

Ant Diversity and Community Composition from North-West Himalayas

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Abstract

The present research work focused on the ant diversity and community composition from North-West Himalayas. A total of 35 species of ants belonging to 22 genera and 5 subfamilies were recorded. Of the five recorded subfamilies, Myrmicinae was the most diverse, (16 species), followed by Formicinae with 12 species. Subfamily Dolichoderinae, Ponerinae and Dorylinae are considerably less diverse, with 3, 3 and 1 species respectively. On the basis of the functional group scheme, ants were classified into: generalized myrmicinae, opportunists, subordinate camponotini, climate specialists, cryptic species, and specialist predators. A significant degree of endemism and diversity of the ant fauna was found in the region, with 3 endemic species reported during the current study. But the region is highly prone to anthropogenic activities, as 3 invasive species were also recorded from the region. 2 species of ants *Colobopsis longi* (Forel, 1902) and *Leptogenys lucidula* (Emery, 1895) are being reported for the first time from the Himachal Pradesh. *Colobopsis longi* has been reported from Northeastern India. While *Leptogenys lucidula* has been reported from Sikkim, Uttarakhand, and West Bengal. The presence of these species in the study area can be a range extension due to climatic factors because this is a common phenomenon in many species, including *Colobopsis longi* & *Leptogenys lucidula*. Various climate factors, like changes in temperature, changes in precipitation, increased CO₂ levels, microhabitat changes etc. might contribute to altering the environmental conditions that allow species to expand into new areas. The study represents one of the most comprehensive surveys of the ant fauna undertaken in the region.

Key words: Abundance, Ant, Community composition, Diversity, Formicidae, Hymenoptera, Invasive species

Introduction

Ants originated during the Cretaceous period approximately 168,000,000 years ago (Moreau *et al.*, 2006). There are currently 16,779 ant species belonging to 503 genera in 22 subfamilies Worldwide (Bolton, 2024). In India there are 10 subfamilies of ants having 108 genera and 862 species (Bharti, 2024). Ants serve as valuable bio-indicators for evaluating landscape changes and species diversity (Paknia & Pfeiffer, 2011). Due to their wide representation, ease of collection, identification and sensitivity to perturbations and biotic stresses, ants are effective bio-indicator species (Read & Anderson, 2000). Compared to vertebrates, ants exhibit a more subtle response to stress, constituting a substantial part of the animal biomass in terrestrial ecosystems (Hölldobler & Wilson, 1990; Andersen, 1997). Ants are indispensable for proper functioning of most terrestrial ecosystem and resulting ecosystem services (Del Toro *et al.*, 2012). Ants play crucial ecological roles as predators, scavengers, soil aerators, nutrient recyclers and pollinators (Lach *et al.*, 2010; Del Toro *et al.*, 2012; Guénard, 2013). For soil aeration, nutrient transmission and mixing, ants are frequently more significant than earthworms (Lyford, 1963; Gentry & Stiritz, 1972).

Ants were not naturally widespread across continents however, through global trade, they have migrated from their native regions to various parts of the world (Suarez *et al.*, 2005; Ingram *et al.*, 2006). Based on their adaptations for resource availability and competitive relationships with other ant species, ants are categorised into functional groups (Greenslade, 1978). The classification of functional groups is widely utilized to comprehend alterations in the composition of species

resulting from disturbances (Höffmann & Andersen, 2003). Extensive research has been conducted on ants in India. Rajagopal *et al.* (2005) conducted a study to determine the current status of ant biodiversity in farmed, riverside and industrial areas of Sattur taluk, Tamil Nadu. Bharti *et al.* (2013) investigated variation in species density, species richness, abundance and functional-groups composition along an elevational gradient in Jammu-Kashmir Himalaya. They reported that ant species richness raised as elevation first increased, peaked in the middle of elevation, and then declined, creating a mid-elevation peak. Patkar *et al.* (2014) identified 5 ant species from 4 genera in the subfamily Myrmicinae in Maharashtra. Bharti *et al.* (2016a) examined the diversity, species composition, community patterns and the impact of invasive species in Shivalik Mountains of Himalayas. Their findings suggested that even in primary and protected forest regions, the environment is disturbed, degraded, and has a strong anthropogenic effect, resulting in decreased ecosystem health. Bharti *et al.* (2016b) conducted a study on comprehensive and critical list of Indian ants with current known state-wise distribution. Rabeesh *et al.* (2017) worked on the diversity of the ants in Kuttanad region of Kerala, India. Gupta (2019) examined the diversity of ants based on their morphological traits in Jaipur. The study area is unique because of its geographical position, varied landscape, substantial annual rainfall and population density. The study highlighted the impact of anthropogenic activities on the diversity of ants in the area. During this research a thorough and extensive investigation on the diversity and abundance of ants was conducted.

Materials and methods

Study Area

Himachal Pradesh is a hill state in India that lies in the Western Himalayan Mountain range. Shimla District is situated between longitudes 77°00' E and 78°19' E, and latitudes 30°45' N and 31°44' N. The elevation ranges from 300m to 6000m. The collection tours have been carried out in 79 villages falling in the study area from 2023 to 2024 (Table 1). Ants were collected at altitudes between 1267m to 2482m a.s.l. and covering a distance of 350 km within the study area (Fig. 1). Collection of material was done from cultivated areas, forest areas and non-forest areas. The cultivated area comprises agricultural fields and orchards. Crops such as wheat, maize, capsicum, tomato, and pea are commonly produced in this region. The non-forest sites consist of playing fields, pasture land, community parks, colleges and University campuses. Forest area is the region covered with the dense tree canopy. To avoid sampling bias different methods of ant collection were employed such as Winkler extraction method, Pitfall trap method, Leaf litter, Soil core method, Hand picking and baits. The collected material was preserved in 90% alcohol and mounted on triangles for research in accordance with ant taxonomy. All the collected material was identified up to species level with the help of Bingham (1903); Bolton (1994); Radchenko & Elmes (1999); Bharti *et al.* (2012, 2016b) and Bolton (2024) and compared with the reference collection already housed in the laboratory.

Table 1: List of localities visited during collection tour

Localities visited	State	Year	Altitude
Dhagogi	Himachal Pradesh	11/11/2023	1915m
Kainthari	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	2115m
Jayali	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	2214m
Samhaul	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1630m
Kharogra	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1746m
Dev Dhar	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1728m
Neri	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1643m
Kiar Koti	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1642m
Tikar	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1661m

Mongar	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1582m
Johlu ka Jubbar	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1563m
Rogi	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1629m
Cheri	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1671m
Dochi	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1646m
Dunga Jubbad	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1738m
Bathyal	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1728m
Anu	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1773m
Kot	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1826m
Bhotru	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1905m
Manav	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1411m
Shamlog	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1746m
Mohanpur	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1906m
Manla	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1848m
Chaklu	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1886m
Bhatla	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	1890m
Sariya	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	2079m
Sadhora	Himachal Pradesh	18/02/2024	2118m
Baldeyan	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	2181m
Shohal	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	2482m
Rachod	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1953m
Kanda	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1918m
Kanola	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1855m
Karyali	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1794m
Shali	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1696m
Fagla	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1285m
Shari	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1267m
Devla	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1450m
Moolbhaji	Himachal Pradesh	25/02/2024	1429m
Sangti	Himachal Pradesh	16/03/2024	2052.40m
Neri	Himachal Pradesh	16/03/2024	1426.85m
Malav	Himachal Pradesh	16/03/2024	1426.86m
Chabaog	Himachal Pradesh	16/03/2024	1445.89m
Kyargi	Himachal Pradesh	16/03/2024	1400.91m
Manla	Himachal Pradesh	17/03/2024	1668.83m
Hiun	Himachal Pradesh	17/03/2024	1777.40m
Sanog	Himachal Pradesh	17/03/2024	1782.13m
Karondh	Himachal Pradesh	17/03/2024	1727.31m
Jhalti	Himachal Pradesh	11/04/2024	2179.44m
Patenglee	Himachal Pradesh	11/04/2024	2219.73m
Mashobra	Himachal Pradesh	11/04/2024	2251.10m
Shilru	Himachal Pradesh	11/04/2024	2055.70m
Hiranagar	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1940.40m
Sadhog	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1733.85m
Jablog	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1733.85m
Bhanuti	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1775.80m
Panti	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1697.95m
Chanarri	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1770.42m

Janol	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1613.96m
Rori	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1565.02m
Haddo	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1510.41m
Biuont	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1809.80m
Kajol	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1400.49m
Kyargii	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1330.24m
Niun	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1464.07m
Bhako	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1549.68m
Dharkhufar	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1640.88m
Batol	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1705.55m
Bhoun	Himachal Pradesh	12/04/2024	1808.11m
Bharai	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	2070.70m
Pagog	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1925.51m
Golcha	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1597.33m
Kavi	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1503.87m
Naog	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1536.98m
Ragyan	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1820.43m
Tud	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1788.07m
Salech	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1762.30m
Bhont	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1918.40m
Gaggal	Himachal Pradesh	13/04/2024	1608.66m
Summerhill	Himachal Pradesh	24/04/2024	2041.70m

Figure 1: Map showing Study Area

Results

A total of 35 ant species, representing 22 genera and 5 subfamilies, were found in the study area (Fig. 2). Subfamily Myrmicinae had the maximum diversity with 8 genera and 16 species followed by Formicinae with 8 genera and 12 Species (Fig. 7), Ponerinae with 3 genera and 3

species (Fig. 8), Dolichoderinae with 2 genera and 3 species (Fig. 9) and Dorylinae were found least diverse with only 1 species (Fig. 10).

Table 2: List of ants collected from Study Area

Subfamilies: 5, Genera: 22, Species: 35		
Subfamily	Genus	Species
Dolichoderinae	<i>Chronoxenus</i>	<i>Chronoxenus myops</i> (Forel, 1895)
		<i>Chronoxenus wroughtonii</i> (Forel, 1895)
	<i>Tapinoma</i>	<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (Fabricius, 1793)
Dorylinae	<i>Aenictus</i>	<i>Aenictus ceylonicus</i> (Mayr, 1866)
Formicinae	<i>Camponotus</i>	<i>Camponotus kattensis</i> Bingham, 1903
		<i>Camponotus</i> sp. Minor
	<i>Colobopsis</i>	<i>Colobopsis longi</i> (Forel, 1902)
	<i>Formica</i>	<i>Formica gagatoides</i> Ruzsky, 1904
	<i>Lasius</i>	<i>Lasius himalayanus</i> Bingham, 1903
	<i>Lepisiota</i>	<i>Lepisiota capensis lunaris</i> (Emery, 1893)
		<i>Lepisiota integra</i> (Forel, 1894)
		<i>Lepisiota modesta</i> Forel, 1894
	<i>Paratrechina</i>	<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (Latreille, 1802)
	<i>Polyrhachis</i>	<i>Polyrhachis lecteipennis</i> Smith, 1858
		<i>Polyrhachis menelas</i> Forel, 1904
<i>Pseudolasius</i>	<i>Pseudolasius machhediensis</i> Bharti, Gul & Sharma, 2012	
Myrmicinae	<i>Aphaenogaster</i>	<i>Aphaenogaster beelsoni</i> Donisthorpe, 1933
		<i>Aphaenogaster rothneyi</i> (Forel, 1902)
		<i>Aphaenogaster symthiesii</i> (Forel, 1902)
	<i>Cardiocondyla</i>	<i>Cardiocondyla mauritanica</i> Forel, 1890
	<i>Crematogaster</i>	<i>Crematogaster himalayana</i> Forel, 1902
		<i>Crematogaster sagei</i> Forel, 1902
	<i>Messor</i>	<i>Messor himalayanus</i> (Forel, 1902)
	<i>Myrmica</i>	<i>Myrmica hectate</i> Weber, 1947
		<i>Myrmica wittmeri</i> Radchenko & Elmes, 1999
	<i>Pheidole</i>	<i>Pheidole indica</i> Mayr, 1879
		<i>Pheidole sulcaticeps</i> Roger, 1863
		<i>Pheidole woodmasoni</i> Forel, 1885
	<i>Temnothorax</i>	<i>Temnothorax inermis</i> (Forel, 1902)
		<i>Temnothorax rothneyi</i> (Forel, 1902)
<i>Temnothorax simlensis</i> (Forel, 1904)		
<i>Trichomyrmex</i>	<i>Trichomyrmex destructor</i> (Jerdon, 1851)	
Ponerinae	<i>Brachyponera</i>	<i>Brachyponera luteipes</i> (Mayr, 1862)
	<i>Leptogenys</i>	<i>Leptogenys lucidula</i> Emery, 1895
	<i>Odontomachus</i>	<i>Odontomachus monticola</i> Emery, 1892

Table 3: First records to Himachal Pradesh

<i>Colobopsis longi</i> (Forel, 1902)
<i>Leptogenys lucidula</i> Emery, 1895

Table 4: List of Invasive and Endemic species collected from Study Area

Species	Endemic	Invasive
<i>Cardiocondyla mauritanica</i> Forel, 1890		Invasive
<i>Pseudolasius machhedensis</i> Bharti, Gull & Sharma, 2012	Endemic	
<i>Temnothorax inermis</i> (Forel, 1902)	Endemic	
<i>Temnothorax simlensis</i> (Forel, 1904)	Endemic	
<i>Trichomyrmex destructor</i> (Jerdon, 1851)		Invasive
<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (Latreille, 1802)		Invasive

Table 5: List of ant species collected from Study Area

Subfamily	Genus	Species
Dolichoderinae	<i>Chronoxenus</i>	2
	<i>Tapinoma</i>	1
Dorylinae	<i>Aenictus</i>	1
Formicinae	<i>Camponotus</i>	2
	<i>Colobopsis</i>	1
	<i>Formica</i>	1
	<i>Lasius</i>	1
	<i>Lepisiota</i>	3
	<i>Paratrechina</i>	1
	<i>Polyrhachis</i>	2
	<i>Pseudolasius</i>	1
Myrmicinae	<i>Aphaenogaster</i>	3
	<i>Cardiocondyla</i>	1
	<i>Crematogaster</i>	2
	<i>Messor</i>	1
	<i>Myrmica</i>	2
	<i>Pheidole</i>	3
	<i>Temnothorax</i>	3
	<i>Trichomyrmex</i>	1
Ponerinae	<i>Brachyponera</i>	1
	<i>Leptogenys</i>	1
	<i>Odontomachus</i>	1
5 subfamilies	22 Genera	35 species

Table 6: Numerical data of ants collected from Study Area

Species collected from Tehsil Shimla Rural	Specimen Number
<i>Aenictus ceylonicus</i> (Mayr, 1866)	3
<i>Aphaenogaster beesoni</i> Donisthorpe, 1993	64
<i>Aphaenogaster rothneyi</i> (Forel, 1902)	15
<i>Aphaenogaster smythiesii</i> (Forel, 1902)	6
<i>Brachyponera luteipes</i> (Mayr, 1862)	96
<i>Camponotus kattensis</i> Bingham, 1903	102
<i>Camponotus</i> sp. Minor	1
<i>Cardiocondyla mauritanica</i> Forel, 1890	1
<i>Chronoxenus myops</i> (Forel, 1895)	22
<i>Chronoxenus wroughtonii</i> (Forel, 1895)	25
<i>Colobopsis longi</i> (Forel, 1902)	18

<i>Crematogaster himalayana</i> Forel, 1902	5
<i>Crematogaster sagei</i> Forel, 1902	182
<i>Formica gagatoides</i> Ruzsky, 1904	2
<i>Lasius himalayans</i> Bingham, 1903	8
<i>Lepisiota capensis lunaris</i> (Emery, 1893)	53
<i>Lepisiota integra</i> (Forel, 1894)	87
<i>Lepisiota modesta</i> Forel, 1894	2
<i>Leptogenys lucidula</i> Emery, 1895	4
<i>Messor himalayanus</i> (Forel, 1902)	57
<i>Myrmica hectate</i> Weber, 1947	22
<i>Myrmica wittmeri</i> Radchenko & Elmes 1999	1
<i>Odontomachus monticola</i> Emery, 1892	1
<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (Latreille, 1802)	5
<i>Pheidole indica</i> Mayr, 1879	60
<i>Pheidole sulcaticeps</i> Roger, 1879	36
<i>Pheidole woodmasoni</i> Forel, 1885	28
<i>Polyrhachis lacteipennis</i> Smith, 1858	11
<i>Polyrhachis menelas</i> Forel, 1904	1
<i>Pseudolasius machhediensis</i> Bharti, Gul & Sharma, 2012	10
<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	10
<i>Temnothorax inermis</i> (Forel, 1902)	6
<i>Temnothorax rothneyi</i> (Forel, 1902)	2
<i>Temnothorax simlensis</i> (Forel, 1904)	18
<i>Trichomyrmex destructor</i> (Jerdon, 1851)	33

Table 7: Different functional groups with their respective genus

Functional Group	Genus
Generalised Myrmicinae	<i>Crematogaster</i>
	<i>Messor</i>
	<i>Pheidole</i>
Opportunists	<i>Aphaenogaster</i>
	<i>Cadiocondyla</i>
	<i>Formica</i>
	<i>Lepisiota</i>
	<i>Paratrechina</i>
	<i>Tapinoma</i>
Subordinate Camponotini	<i>Polyrhachis</i>
	<i>Camponotus</i>
Cold climate specialists	<i>Chronoxenus</i>
	<i>Lasius</i>
	<i>Temnothorax</i>
Tropical climate specialists	<i>Aenictus</i>
	<i>Pseudolasius</i>
Cryptic species	<i>Lepisiota</i>
Specialist predators	<i>Odontomachus</i>
	<i>Leptogenys</i>

Figure 2: Subfamily representation of 22 genera

Figure 3: Subfamily representation of 35 species

Figure 4: Subfamily representation in terms of number of specimens collected

Figure 5: Functional group representation

Figure 6: Generic richness of Subfamily Myrmicinae in terms of number of specimen and species collected

Figure 7: Generic richness of Subfamily Formicinae in terms of number of specimen and species collected

Figure 8: Generic richness of Subfamily Ponerinae in terms of number of specimen and species collected

Figure 9: Generic richness of Subfamily Dolichoderinae in terms of number of specimen and species collected

Figure 10: Generic richness of Subfamily Dorylinae in terms of number of specimen and species collected

Discussion

A total of 937 ant specimen representing 35 species belonging to 22 genera of 5 subfamilies were collected (Fig. 4). Two species *Leptogenys lucidula* and *Colobopsis longi* were reported for the first time from Himachal Pradesh. This study also accounts range extension of invasive species. These invasive species create an unsettling image because they have developed to occupy a changed and largely deserted habitat that has been left behind by non-environmentally adaptable human cultural evolution. There is a significant degree of endemism and diversity in the ant fauna found in the region. The patterns of diversity and endemism that are emphasized here are crucial to comprehend in order to provide baseline data for any conservation programs. A wide variety of forest types have been able to thrive due to topography variances, historical climatic regimes, and current microclimatic variations. The resulting biodiversity is more likely to have a higher level of environmental adaptation and specialization. The combination of biological isolation, landmass separation and specialization has resulted in a high degree of regional endemism. Nevertheless, because of their restricted ability to disperse, endemic ants in the region are very susceptible to both anthropogenic disturbances and climate change.

Conclusion

An extensive study was conducted to assess the diversity and abundance of ants in the research area. A total of 35 species were identified, spanning 22 genera and 5 subfamilies (Table 2). In terms of species richness, subfamily Myrmicinae was reported to be the largest and most diverse subfamily (Fig. 3). Within the subfamily Myrmicinae, the most prevalent genus was *Crematogaster* (Fig. 6). On the basis of functional group classification, ants were classified into the following functional group scheme: generalized myrmicinae, opportunists, subordinate camponotini, climate specialists, cryptic species, and specialist predators (Fig. 5). The present study reported that of the 22 genera, 6 were opportunists, 5 were climate specialists, 2 were specialist predators, 2 were subordinate camponotini, and only 1 contained cryptic species (Table 7). Specialist predators are important predators and scavengers, helping control pest populations and recycle organic matter. Cryptic species exploit different ecological niches without direct competition. Tropical climate specialists help shape the structure and composition of plant and animal communities in tropical environments. Opportunists are capable of exploiting a broad range of food sources. This allows them to fill gaps in the food web. Cold climate specialists contribute to soil health through their nest-building activities. These ants help control populations of small invertebrates through predation. Generalized Myrmicinae are known for hunting a range of prey. These ants act as scavengers and contribute to the decomposition process.

During the present study, a rare ant genus *Colobopsis* was reported; moreover, two ant species, *Colobopsis longi* (Forel, 1902) and *Leptogenys lucidula* (Emery, 1895), are being reported for the first time from Himachal Pradesh. 3 invasive species were also reported from the study area. The rising number of invasive species in the area due to increased anthropogenic activities is a major cause of concern. The invasive species are a major threat to native species found in the area. If proper measures are not taken, then the invasive species will eventually replace the native species in the area. The study will aid in our comprehension of ant diversity patterns since it also shows the pattern of species richness and abundance in the area. Preliminary data has been generated from this study which will be useful to amateurs and academics that are interested in ant biodiversity or geographic distribution. This study can help to improve public awareness about the relevance of ants. In conclusion, our research on ants and their diversity has the potential to expand scientific understanding across several disciplines, aid conservation efforts, and stimulate further research into the intriguing world of ants.

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